

EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF A RAILWAY TRACK

Aigul Zhangabylova✉

*Department of Institute of Architecture and Construction¹
zhangabylovazhangabylova@mail.ru*

Gulmira Bikhzhayeva

Department of Structural Engineering²

Mikhail Kvashnin

Department of Structural Engineering²

Assel Kurbenova

Department of Institute of Architecture and Construction¹

Kuralay Joldassova

Department of Institute of Architecture and Construction¹

¹*Satbayev University*

22a Satpaev str., Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan, 05013

²*Academy of Logistics and Transport*

97 Shevchenko str., Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan, 050012

✉ **Corresponding author**

Abstract

It is known a priori that vibrations that occur in the elements of the track structure during the passage of a train load are a superposition of free and forced mechanical vibrations. It has been established that the range of oscillation frequencies of the elements of the track superstructure includes oscillations with a frequency from tens to hundreds and thousands of hertz. However, the influence of vibrations on the track and their dependence, in turn, on the design of the track, has not been fully studied, which causes controversy between specialists in this matter. There is an opinion that in intermediate fastenings, the main role is played by an elastic gasket, which ensures the vertical rigidity of the rail-sleeper assembly. It has been experimentally established that in the frequency range below the frequency of free oscillations of rail fastenings, the force applied to the upper surface of the elastic gasket is transferred to the lower surface in an unchanged form.

The article discusses the vibrations that occur in the elements of the upper structure of the track (rails, sleepers, rail fastenings, ballast base) during the passage of a moving load, which significantly affect the strength, and, consequently, the durability of both the elements themselves and the railway track generally. Vibrograms, oscillograms, accelerograms of rail oscillations and their spectra during the passage of TALGO are presented. At present, the VOSSLOH fastening, developed in Germany, has been widely used in the construction of tracks on high-speed railways of the Republic of Kazakhstan. In this regard, there is a need for a comprehensive study of the operation of this type of fastening under a train load.

Keywords: railway track, rail fastenings, mechanical oscillations, vibrations, amplitude-frequency characteristics.

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1. Introduction

Currently, in accordance with the strategy for the development of the transport system of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2030, construction of new and reconstruction of existing railways is underway. One of the directions of the strategy is the development of a network of high-speed and high-speed train traffic. The organization of such traffic on the railway network of the Republic of Kazakhstan is closely related to ensuring the necessary level of reliability of the railway track, both the subgrade and the superstructure of the track, which have a significant impact on the safety of train traffic.

Numerous cases of deformation of railways under conditions of increased axial loads and speeds determine the need to solve the problems of timely identification of the nature and causes of deformations in structural elements. This is due to the fact that destruction and accidents occurring due to deformation processes cause huge economic, social and environmental damage, incomparable with the funds spent on protective measures.

The safety of train traffic is the main condition for the operation of the railway. Violations of traffic safety lead to damage to infrastructure and rolling stock, loss of transported goods, injury to people. Almost all enterprises of the railway transport system are working to ensure traffic safety, using technical means of monitoring the condition of the rolling stock and the railway track.

The increase in the speeds of rolling stock on the railways of the Republic of Kazakhstan imposes increasingly high requirements for the reliability of the railway track. The problem associated with reducing the impact of vibration effects on the upper structure of the track is solved in various directions, including in the direction of creating such intermediate fasteners that would sufficiently isolate sleepers, ballast and the roadbed from harmful vibrations. Such fasteners would reduce the level of dynamic impact of the wheels of the rolling stock on the track with reinforced concrete sleepers.

The results of studies by a number of scientists and specialists [1, 2] indicate the insufficiency of considering only the stresses arising in its elements as the reasons for the accumulation of residual deformations of the track. The paper [2] substantiates the need to take into account the vibrational nature of the impact of the rolling stock on the ballast layer. When creating the main provisions of the calculation for the strength of the railway track in [3–4], the impact of vibration was noted as one of the main factors contributing to the accumulation of residual deformations. However, it should be noted that the vibration component of the train impact significantly affects the subgrade, especially during periods of oversaturation of the soil with moisture in autumn, freezing in winter and thawing in spring. In [5], an attempt was made to «establish the patterns of distribution of vibrodynamic loads under normal conditions and during deep freezing and thawing of soils». An analytical method has been developed for determining the «strength and deformability of the subgrade in the elastic-plastic stage of its operation, taking into account the vibrodynamic impact» [5].

Japanese scientists have studied the influence of vibrations on track design not only theoretically, but also empirically. In particular, when conducting a comparative technical and economic analysis for various structures of the superstructure of the track, they calculated the expected costs for the current maintenance of the track. The following parameters were used in the calculation [6, 7]: the moving load coefficient, determined by the product of the expected tonnage and the speed of trains, and the quantitative characteristic of the rolling stock, and the coefficient of the structure of the track structure, which takes into account the magnitude of the dynamic impact on the ballast under the sleeper and the vibrational accelerations of the ballast. A decrease in the resistance to shear of the ballast along the track from the effect of vertical vibration that occurs during the movement of the rolling stock was revealed by [8].

In world practice, it is customary to evaluate vibration effects on structures by measuring the speed of the oscillatory process [9–13]. This is because this parameter characterizes the energy of seismic waves affecting the structure. The problems of studying the vibration effects of rolling stock on the railway track can be solved quite successfully by methods and means used in technogenic seismic.

Devised at the Moscow Government University of mines chair PhTCM the vibroacoustical method of the nondestructive control has found wide application at defects detection of coverings and blocks bracing with the basis in various areas of techniques (in building, on transport, in mining, in water conservation, etc.).

From various modifications of the given method the shock variant based on the spectral analysis of vibroacoustic impulse, which was recorded on the surface of prototype system is more particularly used in its excitation by mechanical shock [14, 15].

However, all modifications of vibroacoustic method were developed with regard to single-layer physical model of the prototype system defective site, when the volume between a free surface and defect was represented as thin elastic plate, in which bending vibrations are excited on the several first own fashions of plate.

The purpose of this article is to substantiate the possibility of choosing the type of intermediate rail fastenings using the vibration diagnostics method. The task of the study is to perform full-scale measurements of the dynamic characteristics of the railway track with a known axial load from the rolling stock and its speed, in order to identify vibration parameters that most adequately reflect the vibrodynamic processes in the elements of the superstructure of the track.

2. Materials and methods

In connection with this nondestructive control of such layered objects at a considerable thickness of the general elastic layer (40 centimeters and are more), is consisting in detection of possible contact infringement of all construction with the basis. And detection of such defect and its identification by modern methods of nondestructive control directly under production conditions is rather difficult technical problem, and in some cases it is possible only with application vibroacoustic method. In addition, theory of the given method is insufficiently developed now. Bending vibrations of an elastic plate over defect and over the damp basis were theoretically regarded only in case of harmonious excitation of object.

Computer modeling was carried out on the ground of the general theory of oscillatory systems with the distributed parameters in case of harmonious external force and shock influence on an elastic plate. Calculations were spent in the environment of MathCAD. For simplification of calculations of own frequencies bending vibrations of plates, as boundary conditions has been chosen the case, when a rectangular plate rigidly pressed on an outline.

At calculation of oscillatory characteristics of the plate lying on the elastic basis, as the approximation the model of Grigory Borisovich Muravskii has been chosen [16], in which its equivalent oscillatory parameters: rigidity of the basis C and resistance of the basis μ at harmonious fluctuations can be fairly simple defined by elastic characteristics of the real basis:

$$C = 1.53 \sqrt{\frac{S}{\pi}} \frac{E_0}{1 - \sigma_0^2}; \mu = \frac{0.478 \sqrt{(1 + \sigma_0)(3 - 2\sigma_0)}}{(1 - \sigma_0^2)} \cdot S \cdot \sqrt{\rho_0 E_0}, \quad (1)$$

where E_0 – modulus of elasticity (Young's modulus), ρ_0 – material density, σ_0 – Poisson's ratio of a basis material; S – the area of the plate, adjoining to the basis.

Then the module of oscillatory speed of the centre of the plate, lying on the elastic basis, on its basic fashion, according to the general theory of oscillatory systems with the distributed parameters, can be calculated as follows:

$$|\dot{\xi}_{loc}| = \frac{F_0}{\sqrt{\left[\omega_1^2 \cdot \eta \cdot \frac{M_1^*}{\omega^2} + \mu \right]^2 + \omega^2 \left[1 - \frac{1 + C \cdot K_1^*}{\omega^2 \cdot K_1^* \cdot M_1^*} \right]^2}}, \quad (2)$$

where η – ratio of plate material losses; M_1^* , K_1^* – equivalent mass and a pliability of plate on the first fashion.

At shock influence on a plate the module of spectral density vibroacoustic response was defined:

$$|N(f)| = |M(f)| \cdot |S(f)|, \quad (3)$$

where $|S(f)|$ – the module of shock impulse spectrum $F(t)$; $|M(f)|$ – the module of object amplitude-frequency response, in the case of free plate oscillations or on the elastic basis.

Calculations of plates oscillating response spectral density on shock influence as well in a free condition, as lying on the elastic basis have been carried out during the modeling, with variations of elastic properties of the basis and duration of a shock impulse.

Elastic plates parameters correspond to concrete parameters: $E = 1.225 \cdot 10^{10}$ N/m²; $\sigma = 0.17$; $\rho = 2.45 \cdot 10^3$ kg/m³; $\eta = 0.261$. During the process of modeling the value η was diminishing by an order of ($\eta = 0.0261$ ratio of plate material losses). The elastic module of the basis varied in following limits:

$$E_{01} = 8.18 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}^2}; E_{02} = 8.18 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}^2}; E_{03} = 8.18 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}^2}.$$

Other characteristics of the basis corresponded to a case of the consolidated soil basis: $\sigma_0 = 0.34$; $\rho_0 = 1.65 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Change of an elastic plate shock excitation character was considered by a variation in the course of modeling of shock impulse duration.

In addition, the rather important fact has been noticed, which required for realization of the given method, and connected with that the greatest damp fluctuations of plates by the basis takes place on the first basic fashion of the plate fluctuating over defect. And, as the plate thinner, as damp ratio higher in all frequency range, in particular on frequency of the first fashion.

Studying of influence of duration of a shock impulse on oscillatory processes of an elastic plate has shown that in most cases spectra of impulses oscillation response on shock influence have difficult appearances.

This paper presents the results of experimental determination of the dynamic characteristics of the upper structure of the track with a FOSSLOH-type fastening during the passage of «TALGO» at a speed of 97 km/h. The measurements were carried out by specialists of the testing laboratory «Testing of the track and artificial structures» at the Aksenger railway crossing of the Almaty distance of the track (PCH-46), using a mobile vibration measuring complex.

The complex consists of vibration velocity sensors (velocimeters) MV-25D-V, which convert mechanical vibrations acting on them into an electrical signal. The conversion of the analog signal into digital form is carried out in the electronic ADC unit (L-CARD Company, model E-14-440).

Digital data collection from the ADC and general measurement control is implemented using special software of a personal computer such as «Notebook». The general view of the mobile vibration-measuring complex is shown in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1. General view of the mobile vibration-measuring complex

The signal is recorded using the «LGraph2» application software package supplied with the E-14-440 digital module. This package allows recording the amplitude-time characteristics of signals with time synchronization for all channels used simultaneously.

A high degree of accuracy, reliability and adequacy of the research results is confirmed by the use of certified and calibrated measuring instruments, tested and widely used software products in engineering practice, and a sufficient amount of experimental data.

The analog signal from the vibration sensors in the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) is converted into digital form and reduced to real vibration velocity values using calibration coefficients obtained for each sensor during their calibration. The amplitude-time dependences (vibrograms) are constructed for each element separately (for rails, sleepers, rail fastenings). Using the fast Fourier transform (FFT), graphs of the spectral density of the signal dispersion (amplitude-frequency dependences) are plotted – vibration velocity spectra. The mean square value (RMS) of the vibration velocity is calculated. With the help of the numerical integration operation of the amplitude-time dependences of the vibration velocity, graphs of the amplitude-time

dependence of vibration displacements (oscillograms) are plotted, and then, using the FFT, graphs of the vibration displacement spectrum (amplitude-phase-frequency dependences of vibration displacement) are plotted.

Further, after preliminary filtering of the digitized signal from the vibration sensors in the lower frequency range (from 0 to 1000 Hz), using the differentiation operation, graphs of the amplitude-time dependence of vibration accelerations (accelerograms) are plotted. With the use of the FFT, graphs of the amplitude-phase-frequency dependences of vibration accelerations are plotted – the spectra of vibration accelerations (graphs of the spectral density of the dispersion). Vibration acceleration RMS is calculated.

It should be noted that the FFT is an approximation of the real Fourier transform over a finite time interval Δt and, therefore, to improve the accuracy of the approximation, the distance between points should be as small as possible. In addition, FFT algorithms require the number of points to be 2 to the power of N , i.e. $n = 2N$, where N is an integer. As a result, the transition in signal analysis from the time domain to the frequency domain can occur in real time. The problem of spectrum «spreading» is solved by using such a signal recording technology, in which the recording equipment starts and ends recording at a signal level close to zero.

All measuring devices included in the mobile vibration-measuring complex are certified and verified. To determine the conversion coefficients, the vibration sensors were pre-calibrated, according to the calibration results, the sensitivity of the sensors is 75 (mV/mm/s).

To measure vibrations, sensors were installed on the edge and in the middle of the reinforced concrete sleeper, on the sole of the rail between the sleepers, on the outer branch of the FOSSLOH type fastening terminals. A fragment of a railway track with installed sensors is shown in (Fig. 2, 3) shows the moment when the «TALGO» passes through the area with installed sensors. The recording duration τ and the sampling frequency of the signal per channel fd , when measuring the vibrations of the upper structure of the path with a FOSSLOH type bond during the passage of the «TALGO» were: $\tau = 32$ s, $fd = 1.6$ kHz.

Fig. 2. Fragment of a railway track with installed sensors

Fig. 3. The moment of the passage of the «TALGO» on the site with installed sensors

3. Results and Discussion

In the future, the measurement results were stored on the hard drive of the computer in the «txt» format. Because of the translation of the primary data into a text format, they represented the dependence of the voltage values generated by the sensor on time. The transition from voltage values to real values of vibration velocity, the construction of spectra (amplitude-frequency characteristics) of the received signals, as well as the construction of amplitude-time dependencies of displacements and accelerations were carried out in the MATHCAD environment. On the graphs of amplitude-time dependencies (Fig. 4, 5, *a*), negative values correspond to the deviation of the element point from the equilibrium position upwards, positive values correspond to the deviation downwards [3–5].

Fig. 4, 6, *a* show a vibrogram, an oscillogram and an accelerogram of vibrations of the middle of the rail in the span between the sleepers and corresponding graphs of the spectral density of dispersion (Fig. 4, 6, *b*). At the beginning of the vibrogram (Fig. 4, *a*), the amplitude emissions corresponding to the axes of the TALGO locomotive are well traced. The maximum amplitude value of the vibration velocity was 40 mm/s. In the spectrum of the vibrogram (Fig. 4, *b*), spectral emissions in the frequency range from 2 to 11 Hz correspond to the frequency of passage of the axial load.

Fig. 4. Vibrogram of oscillations of the middle of the rail and its spectrum:
a – vibrogram of rail vibrations; *b* – its spectrum during the passage of «TALGO»

In addition, in the vibration velocity spectrum there are spectral emissions in the frequency range from 70–180 Hz caused by harmful vibration effects during the passage of the composition. The maximum values of the movements of the middle of the rail are fixed during the passage of wagons (Fig. 5, *a*). The amplitude during the passage of the locomotive is 0.5 mm, during the passage of wagons – 0.74 mm. Local maxima at frequencies of 5 and 7.5 Hz are pronounced in the displacement spectrum (Fig. 5, *b*).

The maximum acceleration values of the middle of the rail (Fig. 6, *a*) are recorded when passing a locomotive – 8000 mm/s², when passing cars average acceleration – 5000 mm/s². The acceleration spectrum is dominated by high-range frequencies – from 70 to 180 Hz (Fig. 6, *b*).

Analysis of similar graphs of amplitude-time dependencies for the elastic terminal of the intermediate rail fastening FOSSLOH, the end and middle of the sleeper showed the following. The amplitude of the vibration velocity on the outer branch of the elastic terminal is three times less than in the middle of the rail. There are practically no emissions in the high-frequency region in the vibration velocity spectrum. This circumstance indicates that the elastic terminal almost completely extinguishes harmful vibrations. The amplitude of the movements recorded on the outer branch of the elastic terminal is on average 0.6 mm, and the movements from the impact of the locomotive are slightly greater than from the impact of the wagons. In the spectrum of the oscillogram, the same frequencies are traced as in the spectrum of vibrations of the middle of the rail (Fig. 5, *b*) with a small difference in the amplitude values of the spectral density. The maximum values of the accelerations of the oscillations of the outer branch of the elastic terminal were 4500 mm/s². The spectrum of the accelerogram is dominated by frequencies from 60 to 170 Hz, but the nature of the spectrum is somewhat different from the spectrum of oscillations of the middle of the rail – it has a wave-like rise and fall.

Fig. 5. Oscillogram of oscillations of the middle of the rail and its spectrum:
a – oscillogram of rail vibrations; *b* – its spectrum during the passage of «TALGO»

Fig. 6. Accelerogram of oscillations of the middle of the rail and its spectrum:
a – accelerogram of rail vibrations; *b* – its spectrum during the passage of «TALGO»

The average amplitude deviations of the vibration velocity when moving the end of the sleeper up were 12.5 mm/s, when moving down – 8.2 mm/s. The maximum emissions on the vibration velocity spectrum are recorded in the frequency range from 2 to 11 Hz, with the maximum spectral density value at a frequency of 5 Hz, which also corresponds to the frequency of the axial load passage. The average value of the amplitude of the movements of the end of the sleeper was 0.9 mm, which is 0.16 mm more than the amplitude of the movements of the middle of the rail.

The maximum outliers on the graph of the spectral density of displacements coincide in frequencies with outliers on the vibration velocity spectrum. The average value of the acceleration amplitude of the end of the sleeper is 4000 mm/s^2 . The nature of the acceleration spectrum of the end of the sleeper is identical to the nature of the spectrum of the accelerogram on the outer branch of the elastic terminal.

On the vibration diagram of the vibrations of the middle of the sleeper, the time interval of the entry-exit of the axial load is clearly traced. The average value of the vibration velocity amplitude was 6 mm/s . In the spectrum of the vibrogram, local maxima are pronounced at frequencies of 5 and 7.5 Hz .

The oscillogram of vibrations of the middle of the sleeper shows that the bending movements exceed the deflection by 1.2 times. The average values of the displacement amplitude were 0.3 mm . In the waveform spectrum, the maximum spectral emissions are recorded at frequencies of 5 and 7.5 Hz . The average values of the amplitude of accelerations in the middle of the sleeper are 3000 mm/s^2 . The spectrum of accelerations of vibrations in the middle of the sleeper has a complex form: a high frequency range is predominant – from 70 to 220 Hz . In this case, the spectrum has a discrete wavelike character.

It is proposed to take as the diagnosable parameters of vibrations of the elements of the superstructure of the track, along which the comparison of rail fastenings in the junction sections is made:

- peak (sp) and root-mean-square (se) values (hereinafter RMS) of vibration displacement, peak (vp) and RMS (ve) of the vibration velocity of the rail in the center of the sleeper box and in the middle of the sleeper on the track axis, characterizing the bending vibrations of these elements, the mechanical voltage and power of vibrodynamic impact;

- attenuation coefficient (β) of the vibration velocity amplitude of the rail vibrations in relation to the sleeper vibrations, the area of the spectra of the vibration velocity of the rail vibrations (Ar) and the sleeper (Ash) in the frequency range up to 20 Hz and their ratio (γ), characterizing the change in the vibrational power and vibration damping due to dissipation of mechanical energy;

- the ratio of the dynamic forces that arise when the train moves on the rail foot and in the middle of the reinforced concrete sleeper to the corresponding static forces.

The results of experimental studies of the authors of this work are confirmed by comparison with the theoretical studies [17], theoretical and experimental foundations for analyzing the dynamics of the stress-strain state in the upper structure of a railway track, a layered soil medium, as a result of the interaction of components of viscoelastic and heterogeneous semi-constrained bodies.

The vertical components of mechanical oscillations (vibrations) of the elements of the superstructure of the track are investigated, since they make a more significant contribution to the overall spectrum of oscillations (vibrations). In the future, the authors plan to study the horizontal (longitudinal and transverse) components of the oscillatory process.

All the results obtained in this work are aimed at developing methods for assessing the interaction of the track and rolling stock, taking into account the reasons for the loss of the bearing capacity of the track associated with mechanical oscillations (vibrations).

The diagnostic technique proposed by the authors, based on the analysis of the response of track superstructure elements with various types of intermediate rail fastenings to the vibrodynamic effect, makes it possible to select a track design with optimal damping properties.

This is especially true when reconstructing existing railway lines for new and modernized locomotives and cars with increased axial loads and speed characteristics.

Comparative analysis with previous studies in this direction, described in [18–20] confirms the practical value of this article. The results of experimental studies presented in this paper allow to draw the following conclusions:

1. When evaluating the data obtained in the process of experimental determination of the dynamic characteristics of the upper structure of the path, it is necessary to perform their multiparametric analysis. In addition to the amplitude-time dependences of vibration velocity, the amplitude-time dependences of displacements and accelerations, as well as the spectral densities of signals (amplitude-frequency characteristics) are of interest [21, 22].

2. FOSSLOH type rail fastening, almost completely extinguishes harmful vibrations that occur during the passage of the «TALGO», in particular, at a speed of about 100 km/h . For a more detailed study of the operation of this type of rail fastening, it is necessary to conduct additional studies at different speeds and values of the moving load.

3. Based on the data obtained using a mobile vibration measuring system; it is possible to evaluate the work of rail fasteners of various types.

4. It is advisable to conduct similar studies for the roadbed of embankments along the entire diameter from the main platform to the sole. This is especially true for problematic embankments, including those consisting of sands of various fractions, in the Khorgas-Zhetygen section. Specialists of IL «IPiIS» repeatedly during the summer and autumn of 2012 took part in visual commission inspections of these sections of the way and the development of recommendations. The physicommechanical properties of the sands composing these mounds were determined using laboratory equipment. We are ready to purchase licensed programs and make calculations of the stability of embankments. Moreover, during the construction of the new Zhezkazgan-Saksaulskaya railway, about 180 km. the tracks are also designed in mobile sands and the data obtained would allow avoiding possible errors during this construction.

The reliability of the embankments can be verified by observing the precipitation of the track during the passage of trains. Here, load tests of the track will be useful to determine the amount of sediment of the track at set speeds and their comparison with the normative ones. It is also necessary to assess the stability of embankments during vibration from trains in the form of sliding of the embankment edge soil.

4. Conclusions

1. The type of intermediate rail fastening significantly affects the quantitative characteristics of the response of the track structure to the vibrodynamic impact of the rolling stock. As the main criteria for quantitative assessment of the vibrodynamic impact of the rolling stock on the track in order to compare the dynamic operation of the track with various types of intermediate rail fastenings, it is recommended to take the peak and root-mean-square values of the vibration displacements and vibration velocities of the rail sole in the center of the intersleeper box and in the middle of the sleeper; as additional – the attenuation coefficient of the amplitude of the vibration velocity of the rail oscillations in relation to the vibration velocity of the sleeper oscillations and the area of the spectra of the vibration velocity of the rail and sleeper oscillations in the frequency range up to 20 Hz.

2. Implementation of the proposed method of vibration diagnostics will make it possible to carry out an express analysis of the state of the railway track in sections with different types of rail fastenings in terms of dynamic parameters and will make it possible to make the most optimal decisions when planning work on the current maintenance and repair of the track, taking into account the impact of rolling stock.

3. Evaluation criteria obtained during the vibration diagnostics of the superstructure of the track with various types of rail fastenings adequately reflect the technical condition of the track and are consistent with the scoring of the track based on the results of the passage of the track measuring car.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data availability

Manuscript has associated data in a data repository.

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